

A Silent Storm: The Unexpected Face of Lupus in Critical Care

Angelo Salvatore Materia^{1*}, Tejas R Bokka¹, Lorin Berman², Samatha N Kasturiarachchi¹, Pathik V Patel¹, Cesar Orlando Ortiz Bernard¹, Orlando A Rodriguez Jr¹, Prachi Anand^{1,3}, Ofek Hai²

¹Department of Internal Medicine at Nassau University Medical Center

²Department of Cardiology at Nassau University Medical Center

³Department of Rheumatology at Nassau University Medical Center

Citation: Angelo Salvatore Materia, Tejas R Bokka, Lorin Berman, Samatha N Kasturiarachchi, Pathik V Patel, Cesar Orlando Ortiz Bernard, et al. A Silent Storm: The Unexpected Face of Lupus in Critical Care. *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour.* 2025;4(6):1-10.

Received Date: 17 June 2025; **Accepted Date:** 20 June 2025; **Published Date:** 22 June, 2025

***Corresponding author:** Angelo Salvatore Materia, Department of Internal Medicine at Nassau University Medical Center

Copyright: © Angelo Salvatore Materia, Open Access 2025. This article, published in *Int Clin Med Case Rep Jour (ICMCRJ)* (Attribution 4.0 International), as described by <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic autoimmune connective tissue disease characterized by an intense inflammatory response that can affect virtually all organs, including the heart. Cardiac involvement in SLE can manifest as pericarditis, myocarditis, and endocarditis, with pericardial involvement being the most common. This case report discusses a 61-year-old male with previously undiagnosed SLE who presented with large pericardial effusion with tamponade physiology as an initial presentation of underlying SLE. We aim to discuss the management that helped reveal the underlying diagnosis and to discuss the importance of diagnosing SLE before progressing to pericardial fluid effusion with tamponade physiology as seen in our patient.

Keywords: Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE); Heart; Physiology

INTRODUCTION

Systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) is a chronic autoimmune disease characterized by immune complex deposition and autoantibody-mediated inflammation, leading to widespread multisystem involvement. According to Jingru et al, there is a global incidence of 5.14 per 100,000 per person and 0.4 million people are newly diagnosed annually.^[1] Lupus can present with a myriad of non-specific symptoms. Most patients may initially present with fever, fatigue, and malaise, but lupus can affect multiple areas of the human body such as mucocutaneous, musculoskeletal, renal, hematological, and cardiac organ systems. As a result, diagnosing lupus can be difficult due to different clinical manifestations. However, it is commonly diagnosed with the presence of autoantibodies, with ANA as the most common screening test as it is the most sensitive. Anti-dsDNA has shown to have a specificity of 95% but does not necessarily present in all cases.^[2,3] Other lab findings include decreased complement levels, elevated inflammatory markers such as ESR and CRP, and leukopenia. Due to

variability in its presentation, it is important to ensure different imaging and lab results are collected for specific organ systems.

Cardiac complications are among the most frequent and clinically significant non-cutaneous manifestations, contributing to both morbidity and mortality. Non-coronary cardiac involvement may include pericarditis, myocarditis, valvular disease such as Libman-Sacks endocarditis, and arrhythmias. Among these, pericardial disease is the most common and is observed in up to 50% of patients on echocardiography. Patients may present with pleuritic chest pain, particularly reproducible by changes in body position, though often presents asymptotically.^[4,5,6]

Pericardial effusions in SLE are typically exudative and immune-mediated, often occurring during active disease flares. While most are hemodynamically insignificant, they can occasionally progress to cardiac tamponade—a life-threatening condition marked by elevated intrapericardial pressure that restricts ventricular filling and reduces cardiac output.^[7] Although tamponade is rare in SLE, occurring in less than 1–3% of patients, it is associated with significant morbidity and may represent the initial clinical manifestation in previously undiagnosed individuals.^[8,9,10-12]

Clinically, tamponade may present with hypotension, jugular venous distension, and muffled heart sounds—Beck’s triad—although these signs may be absent or subtle. Echocardiography remains the gold standard for diagnosis, often demonstrating right atrial or right ventricular diastolic collapse and respiratory variation in transvalvular inflow velocities. Pericardiocentesis provides both diagnostic clarity and therapeutic relief.^[7,13]

This case report describes a 61-year-old male who presented with cardiac tamponade as the initial manifestation of previously undiagnosed SLE. While rare, this presentation highlights the importance of considering autoimmune conditions in the differential diagnosis of unexplained pericardial effusions, particularly in patients without a known rheumatologic history.^[14,15,16]

CASE

A 61-year-old male with a past medical history of hypertension, hyperlipidemia, and immune thrombocytopenic purpura presented to the emergency room with altered mental status and lethargy. Initial vitals on presentation included a blood pressure (BP) of 112/77 mmHg, heart rate (HR) of 120 beats/min, respiratory rate (RR) of 25 breaths/min, and a temperature of 98.8 F, while saturating at 94% on room air. The patient’s BP dropped to 74/46 mmHg and became tachycardic to 115 beats/min. He received 3 liters of normal saline with subsequent improvement of his BP. He became febrile to 101.7 F and received one dose of piperacillin-tazobactam 4 gram-0.5 gram once via IV and vancomycin 1 gram via IV by the ER staff. Initial EKG was remarkable for sinus tachycardia, right axis deviation, and low voltage in the extremity and precordial leads (Figure 1). Initial chest imaging showed bilateral pleural effusion on the left greater than the right without exclusion of possible underlying consolidation. Lab work on admission was remarkable for anemia, thrombocytopenia, hyponatremia, elevated lactate, transaminitis, and proteinuria on urinalysis (Tables 1-5). The patient was initially admitted overnight under the care of the medicine service.

Figure 1: EKG on admission showing sinus tachycardia, right axis deviation, and low voltage in the extremity and precordial leads.

Table 1: Initial labs and trended labs if applicable with normal ranges denoted in parentheses. Normal lab values used are from American College of Physicians (ACP).

Lab	Initial lab value	Trended lab (if applicable)
WBC	6,140 u/L (4000-10,000 u/L)	
Hemoglobin	6.4 g/dL (14-17g/dL)	
Hematocrit	20.2% (41-51%)	
MCV	86 fL (80-100 fL)	
RDW	17.2% (11.5-14.5%)	
Platelets	76,000/uL (150,000-400,000 u/L).	
Na	130 meq/L (136-145 meq/L)	
K	4.8 meq/L (3.5-5 meq/L)	
Cl	98 meq/L (98-106 meq/L)	
Bicarb	24 meq/L (23-28 meq/L)	
Anion Gap		8
BUN	34 mg/dL (8-20 mg/dL)	
Creatinine	1.1 mg/dL (0.7-1.3 mg/dL)	
eGFR	>60 mL/min/1.73m ² (130 mL/min/1.73 ²)	
Blood Glucose	114 mg/dL (70-100 mg/dL)	
ALT/AST/ALP	89/226/137 units/L (0-35/0-35/36-93 units/L)	
Total Bilirubin	0.6 mg/dL (0.3-1.2mg/dL)	
Albumin	2.1 g/dL (3.5-5.5 g/dL)	
High Sensitivity Troponin	17 ng/L (<14 ng/L)	18 ng/L
Magnesium	1.8 meq/L (1.5-2.4meq/L)	
Phosphorus	2.8 mg/dL (3-4.5 mg/dL)	
Creatine Kinase	180 umol/L (61.9-115 umol/L)	

Lactate	2.9 mmol/L (0.67-1.8 mmol/L)	
TSH	1.61 mU/L (0.5-5 mU/L)	
Thyroxine (total)	4.4 ug/dL (5-12 ug/dL)	
Procalcitonin	1.65 ng/dL (<0.05 ng/dL)	
LDH	223 units/L (60-160 units/L)	
INR	1.6 (0.8-1.1)	
aPTT	38.7s (25-35s)	

Table 2: Results of various cultures and urine studies obtained during the admission. As noted above, normal ranges are in parentheses.

Labs/specimens	Results
Urinalysis	Negative for infection. Significant proteinuria present.
Urine Culture	Candida Albicans (10-25k CFU)
Blood Culture	No growth to date
MRSA	Negative
Influenza A	Negative
Influenza B	Negative
SARS-COVID	Negative
Serum Osm	285 mOsm/kg H ₂ O (275-295 mOsm/kg H ₂ O)
Urine Osm	695 mOsm/kg H ₂ O (50-1200 mOsm/kg H ₂ O)
Urine Na	147 meq/24h (100-260 meq/24h)
Urine Creatinine	18 mg/kg per 24h (15-25 mg/kg per 24h)

Table 3: Results of pericardial and pleural fluid analysis including culture results obtained from each specimen.

<u>Pericardial Fluid Analysis</u>	
CMV culture	Negative
HSV 1&2 Culture	Negative
Hepatitis C AB	Negative
Albumin	1.3 g/dL (1.19-3.06 g/dL)
Triglycerides	34 mg/dL (<50 mg/dL)
Adenosine Deaminase (ADA)	16.2 U/L (<40 U/L)
AFB	Negative
Culture growth	No growth to date
<u>Pleural Fluid analysis</u>	
pH	7.9 (7.60-7.64)
Protein	3.6 g/dL (1-2 g/dL)
Glucose	131 mg/dL (70-100 mg/dL)
Amylase	49 U/L (30-110 U/L)
WBC	52 mm ³ (<1000 mm ³)
LDH	390 units/L (<50% of serum LDH)

AFB	Negative
Pleural Biopsy	Negative for malignancy or infection. Biopsy showed fibrous-adipose tissue with reactive mesothelial changes and patchy lymphoplasmacytic infiltrates. Immunostains revealed positivity of AE1/3 for reactivity lining of the epithelium and negative for calretinin and CD34
Pericardial Biopsy	Negative for malignancy or infection.

Table 4: Rheumatology panel obtained during admission with results noted in the right column. Normal levels noted in parenthesis if applicable.

<u>Rheumatology Panel</u>	
ANA	0.930555556
SS-A	Positive (2.5, ref range<1)
SS-B	Negative
dsDNA	Positive (1:1280)
Mitochondrial	Negative
Smooth Muscle AB	Negative
Rheumatoid Factor	Negative
CCP AB	Negative
RNP	Negative
Jo-1	Negative
SCL-70	Negative
Centromere AB	Negative
Histone AB	Positive
Proteinase-3	Positive (2.5, ref range<1)
B2 (IgG, IgM, IgA)	Negative
Cardiolipin (IgM, IgG)	Negative
Lupus Anticoagulant	Negative
Haptoglobin	144 mg/dL (50-150 mg/dL)
Complement C3c	10 mg/dL(55-120 mg/dL)
Complement C4c	<2 mg/dL (15-46 mg/dL)
IgM	233 mg/dL (20-140 mg/dL)
IgG	2012 mg/dL (640-1430 mg/dL)
IgA	349 mg/dL (70-300 mg/dL)
IgE	12 IU/mL (<150 IU/mL)
IgD	<7 mg/dL (<8 mg/dL)

Table 5: Results from protein electrophoresis obtained during admission. Normal levels noted in parentheses.

<u>Protein Electrophoresis</u>	
Protein	3.8 g/dL (6.4-8.3 g/dL)
Albumin	2.3 g/dL (3.5-5 g/dL)
Alpha-1	0.3 g/dL (0.1-0.3 g/dL)
Alpha-2	0.6 g/dL (0.6-1 g/dL)
Beta	0.3 g/dL (0.7-1.2 g/dL)
Gamma	1.9 g/dL (0.7-1.6 g/dL)

On presentation the patient was able to answer simple questions but could not provide any detailed significant history as he was recently discharged from another hospital after a prolonged hospitalization. Given the patient was also anemic at an Hgb of 6.4, there was concern for possible hemorrhagic pleural effusions and a CT angiography of the chest and thoracic cavity was performed which showed a large pericardial effusion with indeterminate density of the pericardial fluid (Figure 2). There was redemonstration of the pleural fluid and underlying consolidation could not be ruled out. He was started on IV metronidazole 500 mg every 8 hours, IV Vancomycin dosed via trough and IV cefepime 1 gram every 8 hours for broad spectrum coverage. Records were obtained from his previous hospitalization which indicated an extensive hospital course of just under 2 weeks after a fall and COVID infection. Hospital course at that time was significant for bilateral pleural effusions status post right sided thoracentesis with removal of 1.5 liters of serous fluid. Cytology was negative for malignancy, and pleural fluid was exudative via light's criteria and cultures grew cutibacterium. Importantly, an echocardiogram from that hospital visit showed a small pericardial effusion. The patient was discharged on 7 days of oral cephalexin.

During this admission, Cardiology was consulted due to the large pericardial effusion. Bedside POCUS showed a large pericardial effusion with right sided collapse of the heart suggesting tamponade physiology. There was no jugular venous distension on physical exam or evidence of peripheral edema, however heart sounds were muffled on auscultation. Due to transient hemodynamic instability, the patient was transferred to the medical intensive care unit (MICU) for closer monitoring and received IV maintenance fluid and 1 unit of packed red blood cells.

Cardiothoracic surgery was consulted and the patient underwent a pericardial window with initial hemorrhagic pleural fluid of 400cc via a 32 French thoracostomy. A total of 1.1 liters of serous pericardial fluid was drained via the pericardial window. He was monitored in the surgical intensive care unit (SICU) and was noted to have 105cc of output from the pleural fluid thoracostomy and 130cc of output from the pericardial fluid via Jackson-Pratt (JP) drain in the first 24 hours. During the hospital course, the patient continued to receive broad spectrum antibiotics, and an additional 3 units of packed red blood cells was administered. Fluid analysis suggested exudative effusions, however cytology was negative for malignancy and cultures of both pleural and pericardial fluid was negative including AFB analysis (Table 3). Pericardial biopsy showed fibrous-adipose tissue with reactive mesothelial changes and patchy lymphoplasmacytic infiltrates. Immunostains revealed positivity for AE1/3 of the epithelial lining and negative for calretinin and CD34. Further lab work suggested an underlying autoimmune process (specifically SLE) with results significant for positive anti-dsDNA (1:1280) and ANA titer (1:1280) as well as other positive rheumatological lab work which is summarized in Table 4.

Rheumatology was consulted and suspected a flare of previously undiagnosed SLE secondary to pneumonia. IV methylprednisolone was initiated at 30 mg every 12 hours. The patient also received 1 gram of IV Rituximab. He transitioned to PO prednisone 60 mg daily and was started on PO hydroxychloroquine 200 mg every 12 hours. Output from the pericardial and pleural drain improved and they were subsequently removed. Follow up echos showed a reaccumulation of pericardial fluid, however no further surgical intervention was deemed

necessary. The patient received serial transthoracic echocardiograms (TTE) during this admission. Initial TTE showed large pericardial effusion with echogenic material adhered to the epicardial surface to the right ventricular (RV) free wall, consistent with thrombus, and fibrin depositions of metastasis (Figure 3). The final echocardiogram prior to discharge showed a trivial pericardial effusion.

The patient's hospital course was complicated by new onset atrial fibrillation with rapid ventricular response (RVR) within the first 5 days of hospitalization and the patient was started on IV amiodarone drip and was eventually transitioned to PO amiodarone. Blood cultures were negative and one urine culture grew *Candida albicans* (10-25k CFU). The patient was ultimately discharged on PO prednisone, PO hydroxychloroquine, and the rest of his home medications with outpatient follow up appointments with cardiology, nephrology, PCP and rheumatology. Unfortunately, the patient was lost to follow up.

Figure 2: CT Angiography of the chest showing large pericardial effusion and redemonstration of the nonspecific pleural fluid with underlying consolidation unable to be ruled out.

Figure 3: Transthoracic echocardiogram images. The red arrows in the images denote large pericardial effusion circumferential to the heart. There is early diastolic right ventricular collapse.

DISCUSSION

This case emphasizes the diagnosis and management of cardiac tamponade as a presenting manifestation of undiagnosed SLE. SLE is an autoimmune disease mediated by antibodies and can affect many organs especially the kidneys and heart. SLE diagnosis is made by looking at various different antibodies. The most common laboratory evidence of active SLE is a decrease in the complement levels of C3 and C4 and elevated titers in double stranded-DNA (dsDNA). Patients can also develop lupus secondary to medications and the antibody that is most sensitive are anti-histone antibodies. Serositis is a classic manifestation of SLE and pericardial effusions can develop in up to 50% of patients who have been diagnosed with SLE.^[17]

Pericardial effusion is an abnormal accumulation of fluid in the pericardial cavity, which is defined as the space between the visceral and parietal layers of the pericardium. This cavity usually contains 15 to 50 mL of ultrafiltrate plasma in a healthy person.^[17] Various acute or chronic pathologies can lead to disturbances in the pericardial cavity, which can increase the production of pericardial fluid. The most common cause is idiopathic pericarditis, which can account for 80-90% of cases. The remaining 10-20% are typically due to connective tissue diseases/autoimmune diseases (e.g., SLE), cancers, or post-cardiac syndromes. For the patients presenting with cardiac tamponade-like symptoms there is a wide range in how much fluid is required to cause symptoms, sometimes being as little as 100 ml of fluid.^[18] On pericardial biopsy one would find lymphocytes and fibro-collagenous tissue if the etiology is secondary to an autoimmune process.

Management of the accumulation of pericardial effusions includes a pericardiocentesis and pericardial window. Pericardiocentesis is performed in the acute setting with evidence of hemodynamic instability for immediate relief of symptoms. This is in contrast to a pericardial window which is performed if there are concerns of continuous accumulation and the needs for chronic drainage.

In our patient as per documentation, he had pleural effusions which were drained with pigtailed catheters at his prior hospitalization. However, when he was admitted to our facility, he had reaccumulated the pleural effusions and the pericardial effusions increased. Due to the concerns of reaccumulation after the pericardial effusions were drained, a pericardial window was the treatment of choice.

When one sees a patient who comes with pericardial effusions, hypoalbuminemia and proteinuria, one should suspect causes of nephrotic syndromes such as autoimmune diseases like SLE, tuberculosis, and ANCA vasculitis to name a few. In our patient the other work-up for TB, and ANCA vasculitis and HIV were negative.

The patient appeared to have a long-standing history of undiagnosed SLE as evidenced by positive antibodies for dsDNA and ANA. Interestingly, the patient's blood work also showed positivity to histone antibodies. However, after careful review of the patient's medications, the patient was not receiving any medications classically associated with drug induced lupus. This key finding can suggest one of two things; the first being

that the patient had previously been on well-established culprit medications for drug induced lupus, however this is unlikely since the patient was not on any medications for lupus prior to admission. The alternate theory is that the histone antibody was positive because of SLE itself. This is something that has been discussed in prior literature with one study estimating that up to 75% of cases with SLE have positivity to anti-histone antibodies.^[17]

When working up the SLE diagnosis, we used the European Alliance of Associations for Rheumatology (EULAR)/American College of Rheumatology (ACR) classification criteria of 2019.^[17] In our patient his clinical criteria was positive for leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, subacute cutaneous or discoid lupus, pleural and pericardial effusions, low C3 and C4, a positive ANA titer greater than 1:80 and positive for anti-dsDNA. The patient had a score of 29, which confirmed his diagnosis of SLE.

In an acute flare of SLE the initial treatment is steroids. Once the flare is controlled patients are subsequently started on hydroxychloroquine and tapered off steroids. For outpatient follow-up it is important to serially monitor CBC with differentials, CMP, urinalysis, urine protein, urine creatinine, C3, C4 and anti-Ds-DNA. In patients with moderate-to-severe SLE who are unable to taper off prednisone less than 5 mg, there would be discussions for biologics such as rituximab.^[6] Due to the patient's history of pericardial effusion, the patient would need outpatient cardiology follow up with routine echocardiograms, with possible drainage/surgical interventions if the pericardial effusion is reaccumulating. There is significant reduction in mortality and morbidity if patients are diagnosed and treated early on that are presenting with SLE induced pericardial effusions.^[3]

CONCLUSION

The importance of effective history taking and diagnostic workup for SLE cannot be understated. Our case demonstrates the importance of diagnosing SLE early so that patients can be started on optimal therapy. We aimed to highlight the importance of outpatient diagnosis and workup in order to prevent complications such as significant pericardial effusions with tamponade physiology. Management in our patient was aimed at treating the acute flare of SLE as well as addressing the cardiac manifestations in our patient. Our goal was to highlight the important cardiac manifestations of SLE and highlight what can happen when SLE goes undiagnosed for extended periods of time.

REFERENCES

1. Tian, J, Zhang D, Yao X, Huang Y, Lu Q. (2023). Global epidemiology of systemic lupus erythematosus: A comprehensive systematic analysis and modelling study. Ann Rheum Dis. 2023;82(3):351-356.
2. Solhjo M, Goyal A, Chauhan K. Drug-induced lupus erythematosus. StatPearls. 2023.
3. Justiz Vaillant AA, Goyal A, Varacallo MA. Systemic lupus erythematosus. StatPearls. 2023.
4. Maharaj SS, Chang SM. Cardiac tamponade as the initial presentation of systemic lupus erythematosus: A case report and review of the literature. Pediatr Rheumatol Online J. 2015;17;13:9.

5. [Harnett DT, Chandra-Sekhar HB, Hamilton SF. Drug-induced lupus erythematosus presenting with cardiac tamponade: A case report and literature review. Can J Cardiol. 2014;30\(2\):247.e11-2.](#)
6. [Dein E, Douglas H, Petri M, Law G, Timlin H. Pericarditis in Lupus. Cureus. 2019;11\(3\).](#)
7. [Emorinken A, Dic-Ijiewere MO, Izirein HO. Cardiac tamponade, an unusual first presentation of systemic lupus erythematosus: A case report in a rural Tertiary Hospital. Cureus. 2022;14\(8\):e27989.](#)
8. [Stashko E, Meer JM. Cardiac tamponade. StatPearls. 2023.](#)
9. [Alerhand S, Adrian RJ, Long B, Avila J. Pericardial tamponade: A comprehensive emergency medicine and echocardiography review. Am J Emerg Med. 2022;58:159-174.](#)
10. [Jawaid A, Almas A. Cardiac tamponade as initial presentation in systemic.](#)
11. [Gomez Casanovas J, Bartl M, Rincon-Rueda L, Loftis CE, Dulgheru E. At the heart of the diagnosis: A case of systemic lupus erythematosus presenting as cardiac tamponade. Cureus. 2023.](#)
12. [Li W, Frohwein T, Ong K. Cardiac tamponade as an initial presentation for systemic lupus erythematosus. The American Journal of Emergency Medicine. 2017;35\(8\).](#)
13. [Miner JJ, Kim AHJ. Cardiac manifestations of systemic lupus erythematosus. Rheum Dis Clin North Am. 2014;40\(1\):51-60.](#)
14. [Yousefi-Koma H, Jalalian R, Bagheri B. Acute fibrinous constrictive pericarditis and large pericardial effusion as the first manifestation of systemic lupus erythematosus disease in an adult male patient. Clinical case reports. Clin Case Rep. 2023;11\(10\):e7958.](#)
15. [Kruzliak P, Novak M, Piler P, Kovacova G. Pericardial involvement in systemic lupus erythematosus: Current diagnosis and therapy. Acta cardiologica. Acta Cardiol. 2013;68\(6\):629-33.](#)
16. [Goldar G, Garraud C, Sifuentes AA, Wassif H, Jain V, Klein AL. Autoimmune pericarditis: Multimodality imaging. Curr Cardiol Rep. 2022;24\(11\):1633-1645.](#)
17. [Aringer M, Costenbader K, Daikh D, Brinks R, Mosca M, Ramsey-Goldman R, 2019 European League against Rheumatism/American College of Rheumatology classification criteria for systemic lupus erythematosus. Arthritis & Rheumatology. 2019;71\(9\):1400-1412.](#)
18. [Willner DA, Goyal A, Grigorova Y, Sharma S, Kiel J. Pericardial effusion. StatPearls. 2024.](#)